

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Readmission Agreements and the Evolving Landscape of the Externalized EU Return Policies: The Case of Turkey

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List of Abbreviations

AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
DGMM	Directorate General of Migration Management
EC	European Commission
EP	European Parliament
EURA	European Union Readmission Agreements
EUTRA	EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement
EUTS	EU-Turkey Statement
FRIT	Facility for Refugees in Turkey
GAM	Global Approach to Migration
GAMM	Global Approach to Migration and Mobility
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IGO	Intergovernmental Organisation
IOM	International Organization for Migration
JAP	Joint Action Plan
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MPF	Migration Partnership Framework
MSs	Member States
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
N-AVRR	National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
PF	Partnership Framework
PMM	Presidency of Migration Management
RAs	Readmission Agreements
RPTG	Readmission Protocol of Turkey and Greece
TCNs	Third-Country Nationals
TCs	Third Countries
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Abstract

As the European Union (EU) becomes one of the most popular immigration destinations globally, boosting removal rates has become a political priority. In response to the European humanitarian refugee crisis in 2015, a new generation and informal readmission tools were devised to mollify the growing concerns of the EU Member States and address weaknesses in existing readmission agreements supported by externalisation and differentiated integration. The EU return policy is analysed from a non-EU perspective, shedding much-needed light on third countries' cost-benefit calculations reflecting the macro and meso-level analyses. The paper questions how the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (2013) and the EU-Turkey Statement (2016) shape migration management and return policies between the EU and Turkey and the practical and legal implications of their implementation and suspension. Taking Turkey as a case study, the analysis focuses on two critical readmission instruments, namely the Agreement and the Statement and assesses the EU's return and external policy instruments from a de-centring approach. It draws on longitudinal research based on both desk research and fieldwork conducted in three stages (July 2010–March 2013, June 2018–October 2019, January- July 2024) in several provinces of Turkey, including Ankara, Edirne, Izmir and Istanbul.

Keywords: EU return policy, the EU–Turkey Readmission Agreement, the EU–Turkey Statement, externalisation, external differentiated integration, informalisation

1. Introduction¹

For the last three decades, controlling irregular migration has been a priority for the European Union (EU) and its Member States (MSs). It has also become a central pillar of the external dimension of EU cooperation in justice and home affairs. The emergence of the European refugee humanitarian crisis in 2015 brought asylum and forced migration into the spotlight due to the increasing number of arrivals. In 2015 over 1.8 million irregular crossings at EU borders were recorded (Frontex 2017, 18). Addressing irregular migration and increasing the return rates became top priorities at the EU level. The 2015 crisis was instrumentalised in justifying controversial policies regarding irregular migration.

A pivotal component of the EU's strategy has been the externalisation of migration control, which involves shifting the responsibility of managing migration flows to non-EU countries through various agreements and partnerships. Among these, return and readmission policies play a crucial role. The EU readmission agreements (EURAs) aim to facilitate and accelerate the readmission of third-country nationals (TCNs) who reside without authorisation in EU countries, including rejected asylum seekers. Since 2015, traditionally formalised structured agreements have increasingly incorporated informal mechanisms. This shift towards informality reflects a broader trend of differentiated externalisation, where the EU tailors its migration management strategies to the specific contexts and capacities of third countries (TCs).

The paper analyses the EU return policy changes explicitly focusing on readmission agreements (RAs) in three periods: 1990–2003, 2004–2014 and 2015–present. The selected Turkey case offers a compelling case study for understanding the dynamics of the EU's return policy and readmission. Turkey exemplifies TCs' capacities and strategies to resist the EU's externalisation efforts and ability to resist and leverage externalisation, particularly return policy and readmission tools.

Regarding the return policy and readmission dimension, the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA, 2013) is classified as a part of the second period, and the EU-Turkey Statement (2016) was the flagship of the new generation readmission tool. The paper assesses the EU's return and external policy instruments in this framework and analyses TCs' perceptions and strategies to resist EU externalisation efforts with a de-centring approach. Taking Turkey as a case study, the analysis focuses on two critical readmission instruments: the EUTRA and the EUTS.

The paper argues that the EU's return policy started considering the TCs' demands and expectations due to the non-functioning EURAs and adopting external differentiated integration since the 2015-16 European refugee crisis. Accordingly, the EU has adopted more tailor-made, informal, flexible, and differentiated externalisation strategies than formal and standardised cooperation with TCs (Cherubini, 2017; Spijkerboer, 2017; Vitiello, 2020).

There has been continuing political and societal debate and intensive research on RAs (Boswell 2003; Cassarino 2007; Kruse and Trauner 2008; Coleman 2009; Wolff 2014; Cortinovic 2018;

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Carrera et al. 2019). The EUTRA and the EUTS have been intensively analysed from a legal perspective (Göçmen 2014; Eisele 2019; Carrera et al. 2019; Gatti and Ott 2019). While some scholars questioned whether the EUTS is an international agreement or a political statement (Heijer and Spijkerboer 2016; Arribas 2017; Peers 2017), some focused on the EUTS's incompatibility with international and European refugee law and human rights law standards (Amnesty International 2017; Öztürk and Soykan 2019; İneli-Ciğer and Ulusoy 2020; Ovacık et al. 2024). Nevertheless, the multi-level dynamics of the EU's relations with neighbouring countries and the capacity of agencies that EU externalisation policy targets remain underexplored. Also, there has been little comparative research on the EUTRA and EUTS together and none that offers longitudinal and concrete empirical data to advance our knowledge in the field.

This study draws from primary and secondary sources, as well as desk and multi-sited fieldwork conducted in three stages as longitudinal research. The fieldwork component was conducted in two tranches (July 2010–March 2013, June 2018–October 2019 and January–July 2024) in several provinces of Turkey (Ankara, Edirne, İzmir and İstanbul)². In total, 96 meso-level interviews were conducted for the first tranche, 41 in the second and 20 for the third tranche.³ The interviewees include high-level state officers, representatives and experts of ministries, directorates, and law enforcement agencies, which have a role in border management and the readmission process, institutions related to EU–Turkey relations, and intergovernmental organisations (IGOs) and NGOs.

This longitudinal case study enhances our understanding of readmission arrangements and externalisation policies by showcasing Turkey's strategic use of conditionality in EU negotiations. It contributes to the broader discourse on EU migration policy by elucidating the evolving externalisation strategies and addressing the macro and meso-level perspectives of relevant actors involved in the EUTRA and the EUTS processes and implementation through comprehensive fieldwork.

2. Conceptual and Theoretical Framework: Externalisation and External Differentiated Integration

The EU strives to develop strong partnerships with neighbouring countries irrespective of their potential for EU membership, aiming to foster stability and prosperity in these regions and within the EU. In this regard, by the 2000s, the “externalisation” concept emerged as a broader notion that captured the idea of EU influence beyond its territory through the export of EU forms of political organisation and governance to states not necessarily subject to prospective EU membership (Olsen 2002, Lavenex and Uçarer 2004). The concept implies that TCs adopt parts of the EU acquis in their national legal framework without being offered membership (Rijpma and Cremona 2007; Lavenex and Schimmelfennig 2009).

In the migration and asylum policy domain and from a critical point of view, externalisation aims to prevent irregular migrants, including asylum seekers, from entering the legal

² The field studies were conducted respectively as part of the doctoral research of the author (completed with A Multi-Level and Multi-Sited Analysis of the European Union's Immigration and Asylum Policy Concerning Irregular Migration and Its Implications for Turkey” dissertation, <http://etd.lib.metu.edu.tr/upload/12616581/index.pdf>), (completed with the and the following two EU funded research projects, called “RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (Horizon2020)” (<https://www.respondmigration.com/>) and “GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” (<https://www.returnmigration.eu/>).

³ Not all the interviews provided direct focus on the article's focus, but they provided important insights regarding the implementation processes. All necessary ethics approvals by the Middle East Technical University (PhD. research, İstanbul Bilgi University (RESPOND Project) and Özyeğin University (GAPs Project) are provided.

jurisdictions of the EU or to render such migrants legally inadmissible without considering the individual merits of their protection claims (Frelick et al. 2016). The “containment” (Aleinikoff 1992) refers to “instruments and arrangements aimed at preventing access, reducing admission and increasing the expulsion of asylum seekers to countries of transit or origin as including restrictive visa requirements, carrier sanctions, the use of the ‘safe third country’ concepts, readmission agreements and arrangements” (Tan and Vedsted-Hansen 2021, 7).

One of the key elements of this policy is to convince the TCs to export the EU’s policies; thus, “conditionality”, a “bargaining strategy of reinforcement by reward, under which the EU provides external incentives for a target government to comply with its conditions” (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2004, 670). For the countries with membership prospects, the full membership can be seen as an essential innovation, but regardless of the membership dimension, the size and reliability of the reward are significant against the cost of compliance (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2005). Conditionality is also related to the bargaining power of the EU and the TCs concerning the degree of mutual dependence. From a decentralised perspective, recent studies focus on the bargaining and even “coercive” power or diplomacy of the TCs (Teitelbaum 1984; Greenhill 2010; Tsourapas, 2017; Gokalp Aras 2019a, 2019b) or framing as “reversed conditionality” (Cassarino 2007; Janvier 2023).

RAs have been the cornerstone of the EU’s externalisation policies. Analysis of the content, negotiation and implementation of RAs is typically framed as part of the EU’s ‘burden-shifting’ in its cooperation with TCs (Boswell 2003; Coleman 2009). This cooperation aims to control borders to block arrivals, but where this is not possible, to help transit and source countries outside of EU borders in readmitting migrants and managing the reception of asylum seekers (Geddes 2005; Thym 2013; Triandafyllidou and Dimitriadi 2014).

The Syrian mass migration and subsequent humanitarian refugee crisis in Europe gave more weight to external cooperation. This development started a new phase of EU externalisation when the crisis-driven ‘the state of exception became the new normal’, and the EU embarked on a differentiated integration policy to the needed flexibility to provide itself, the MS, and the TCs to overcome policy deadlocks within the EU (Gokalp Aras 2021).

Differentiated integration is a flexible form of integration frames that MS and non-EU states converge at different speeds in different EU policy areas with ‘ins’ and ‘outs, encompasses ‘all forms of participation below the threshold of full membership’ (Lavenex and Krizic 2019, 3). External differentiation integration refers to some TCs selectively joining existing EU arrangements or regulatory structures in specific policy areas such as the internal market or the Schengen Area (ibid.). It allows TCs to “opt-out” and “opt-in” to policy proposals in the external area, which offers these countries a degree of agency that had hitherto been lacking. The external differentiated integration approach also includes incentives for TCs to join initiatives in specific sectors ‘exporting’ models devised in the EU to control and prevent unwanted population movements (Holzinger and Tosun 2019, 643).

Externalisation has generally foregrounded the powerful position of the EU vis-à-vis relatively weak target countries. Thus, as a part of the externalisation and return policy, RAs bring ‘unbalanced reciprocities and different benefits for the EU and the signatory countries’ (Cassarino 2010a, 2010b). However, as the EUTRA and the EUTS show, rather than being a passive policy receiver, Ankara has geared its policy decisions in this field towards the rational achievement of strategic aims, which means that instrumental considerations have been front and centre. Turkey has continuously tried to resist EU conditionality, the ‘carrots’ of which have been prospective membership, visa liberalisation, and financial aid to address the asymmetric burdens born by Ankara (Rumelili 2004; Özçürümez and Şenses 2011; Tolay 2012). The unprecedented waves of migration toward European shores have also opened opportunities to Turkey and other source and transit countries, which has been central to shifts in the EU’s return policy and related tools.

3. EU Readmission Agreements: Origins, Objectives and Changes

The EU's readmission policy can be analysed from 1990 to 2003, 2004 to 2014, and 2015 to the present. The efforts to tackle irregular migration via return and readmission initiatives started in the 1990s in EU policy-making. In the first period (1990–2003), the critical developments were the Schengen Agreement (1985), which abolished internal borders and the Dublin Convention (1990) with its “safe third-country rule”. The first-generation agreements were readmission clauses included in trade and cooperation agreements between the European Community and TCs rather than formal RAs (Cortinovis 2018, 4; Coleman 2009).

In the second period (2004–2014), cooperation with the TCs intensified, and from 2004, the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) emerged as a framework for externalisation and return policies. The first formal RA was signed in 2004, launching the second generation of EURAs. Since then, the EU has completed 18 RAs⁴, including with Turkey, in 2013. In December 2005, the European Commission published its Global Approach to Migration (expanded as GAMM in 2011), which addresses irregular migration and human trafficking and manages migration and asylum through cooperation with TCs. In response, the Mobility Partnerships (MPs) were introduced by the EC in 2007 as the standard framework for migration cooperation with TCs (European Commission 2007). The GAMM (European Commission 2011) resulted in MPs with several countries' political agreements encompassing various issues, including readmission cooperation.⁵

The last period (2015–present) reflects the impact of the European humanitarian refugee crisis. TCs have become directly involved in EU policy-making. In this period, external differentiated integration has become more visible in addressing obstacles during the negotiation and implementation stages of EURAs (Cassarino 2007; Coleman 2009; Carrera 2016). The EURAs have proven ineffective, with return rates falling short of expectations. Alternative cooperation methods for readmissions have emerged in response to the European humanitarian refugee crisis. These methods include administrative arrangements, bilateral deals, and memoranda of understanding, which substitute formal readmission agreements. Informal, non-binding formats like standard operating procedures facilitate swift returns when formal agreements cannot be promptly concluded or implemented (Cassarino and Giuffré 2017; Cortinovis 2018, 3). Unlike formal treaties, they belong to soft law, creating expectations for compliance and conditionality, where cooperation on readmission is linked to benefits or sanctions, such as visa facilitation or restrictions.

The period started with the EU Action Plan on Return (European Commission 2015), which recognised that an effective return system for the readmission of irregular migrants should be prioritised concerning TCs. Then, the EC published a new communication for the new partnership framework (PF) with TCs under the European Agenda on Migration in 2016 (European Commission 2016a). This communication foregrounded tailor-made arrangements to address each case: “coherent EU and Member State coordination on readmission where the paramount priority is to achieve fast and operational returns, and not necessarily formal readmission agreements” (ibid., 7). Since then, numerous partnerships and informal deals,

⁴ EUTRAs as of July 2024: Hong Kong SAR (2004), Macao (2004), Sri Lanka (2005), Albania (2006), Russia (2007), Ukraine (2008), North Macedonia (2008), Bosnia & Herzegovina (2008), Montenegro (2008), Serbia (2008), Moldova (2008), Pakistan (2010), Georgia (2011), Armenia (2014), Azerbaijan (2014), Turkey (2014), Cape Verde (2014) and Belarus. In addition to these agreements, legally non-binding readmission arrangements have also been concluded with: Afghanistan, Guinea, Bangladesh, Ethiopia, The Gambia, Ivory Coast (European Commission 2020d).

⁵ Notably Moldova (2008), Capo Verde (2008), Georgia (2009), Armenia (2011), Azerbaijan (2013), Morocco (2013), Tunisia (2014), Jordan (2014), and Belarus (2016).

mainly political agreements covering various issues, including readmission cooperation, have been concluded at the EU level.⁶

On the other hand, the MSs have also been increasingly using these non-standard readmission agreements. As of July 2024, 344 bilateral agreements, both including standard and non-standard, were concluded that were linked to readmission states with non-EU countries, from the EEC-12 (which was only 23) to the EU-27, January 2023 (Cassarino et al. 2023, 22).

In 2016, the Resolution of the European Parliament (EP) was adopted to increase the efficiency of readmissions and to ensure the coherence of returns at a European level that requires the adoption of new EU readmission agreements, which should take preference over bilateral agreements between MSs and TCs” (European Parliament 2016). The EC introduced the Migration Partnership Framework (MPF) communication in the same year, which included enriched instruments and resources (European Commission 2016c).

In March 2017, the EC’s new communication stressed the logic behind this period, “well-designed, flexible and streamlined instruments to address migration challenges” (European Commission 2017a, 8). In the same year, a Renewed Action Plan on Returns (European Commission 2017b) was introduced that presents recommendations on making returns more effective by working with TCs to solve the challenges of readmission. In 2018, the EC proposed a new EU Return Directive (European Commission 2018) to recast the Return Directive, but have yet to culminate in a finalised piece of legislation (Gökalp Aras et al. 2024).

In 2020, the EC’s new communication, the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum (the Pact), was introduced (European Commission 2020a) and adopted in 2023 by the EP and the Council. One of the critical components of this Pact is the return, which gives political priority to enhancing return rates and managing migration more efficiently. Considering existing problems in finalising and implementing RAs, the Pact emphasises that the EU should mobilise all its potential policies, tools, instruments and incentives to enhance cooperation on readmission (ibid.).

Adopting Regulation 2021/947 in June 2021 established the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument, calling for a “leverage-based approach” to migration. This strategic shift reflects a move from a normative to a more flexible approach in the EU’s readmission policy but also potentially jeopardises the initial project of consolidating a European common readmission policy in line with EU treaties and international law (Carrera 2016).

The most important characteristic of the new and ongoing period regarding readmission tools and third generation of agreements is “informality” (Cassarino 2007, Tan and Vedsted-Hansen 2021, EuromedRights 2021, Gökalp Aras 2021, Poli 2023, Frasca and Roman 2023, Cassarino et al. 2023, Demirbas and Miliou 2024). Cardwell and Dickson (2023, 3122) define “formal informality” as “the appearance of formality, insofar as resembling familiar or established tools (Regulations, Directives, international agreements), but lacking the procedural safeguards, transparency and classification provided by law and legal processes. In particular, due to the third country’s resistance, reversed conditionality and coercive migration diplomacy, there has been an increasing reliance on informal agreements favouring flexibility for both parties and allowing easier negotiations (Euromedrights 2021).

⁶ Since 2015 three Common Agendas on Migration and Mobility were signed with Nigeria (2015), Ethiopia (2015), and India (2016). Also other forms of agreements were elaborated, such as a Joint Communiqué (Côte d’Ivoire (2016), Mali (2016), Joint Migration Declaration (Ghana (2016), Niger (2016)), Standard Operating Procedures (Mali (2016), Bangladesh (2017), and Good Practices (Ghana (2017), Guinea (2017), the Gambia (2018), Admission Procedures for the Return (Ethiopia (2018), EU Turkey Statement (2016), Joint Way Forward (Afghanistan (2016), the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Tunisia (2023) and the Joint Declaration on the Strategic and Comprehensive Partnership with Egypt (2024).

Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (2021) provide a typology for the EU's new arrangements by arguing that the informalisation of the new generation of return instruments is strategically "designed to avoid the triggering of substantive EU law, thus potentially placing EU activities beyond the pale of EU law", which weakens transparency and accountability with the increased number of actors in implementation (Ibid., 57, 58). Casarrino et al. (2023) provide a more systematic typology under "The EU's Readmission System's Hybridity" that classifies two types of agreements: formal and informal. The non-standard informal ones are "secret agreements not ratified by national parliaments", "informal agreements that can feed into repressive practices and human rights abuses", and "documents may include clauses regarding cooperation on other matters" (ranging from trade or military cooperation to defence, energy security, etc.) (Ibid., 12). This hybrid system, driven by different intentions and factors, is more complex, with TCs now aware of interdependencies and using migration issues as coercive foreign policy tools.

The driving forces behind this hybrid system with more informalisation are often justified both by the EU and also the MSs as the need for "more effectiveness", "practical cooperation", and "to sustain a modicum of international cooperation despite uncertainties" as well as avoiding longer and complicated ratification procedure (Ibid., 23, 25). They are often embedded in broader frameworks of cooperation that include trade, security, and development aid, offering various incentives to TCs (Cassarino et al. 2024).

The rise of informal readmission agreements between the EU and TCs has brought various challenges and consequences. This flexibility allows TCs to express their interests and bypass ratification processes, but it results in a lack of parliamentary oversight in the field of readmission, posing a democratic challenge to the rule of law (Strik 2019; Ott 2020). Additionally, these informal agreements lead to uncertainties in implementation and migrant rights, raising human rights concerns and legal uncertainties (European Ombudsman, 2022). Despite their utility, informal agreements raise concerns about transparency, accountability, and compliance with international human rights standards. Finally, the tools used by the EU do not add significant effectiveness compared to formal readmission agreements due to lack of legal binding, limited accountability, variability in implementation, dependence on the political climate, operational challenges, and lack of monitoring and evaluation (Stutz and Trauner 2021), as the EUTS also sees it. But still, they might sometimes be more effective in facilitating returns than formal agreements, such as bypassing some of the bureaucratic and legal hurdles associated with formal EURAs.

4. The Readmission Aspect in EU–Turkey Relations

A readmission agreement between the EU and Turkey has been on Brussels' agenda since the late 1990s. The first round of negotiations opened in May 2005 but was broken off the following year. Negotiations later resumed and continued in fits and starts until 16 December 2013, when the EUTRA was signed pending ratification (in 2014). Turkey sought visa exemption from the EU countries as part of the deal. However, the MSs' resistance to implementing visa liberalisation saw the EU offer Turkey visa facilitation as an interim remedy, which Ankara saw as insufficient. The EU detailed a list of additional incentives short of full liberalisation in the Roadmap towards a Visa-Free Regime with Turkey in 2013 (European Commission 2016b). Turkey prepared its conditions in the Annotated Roadmap (MFA 2013).

Following the ratification of the EUTRA (2014), the number of entries at the EU border peaked. This development created another shift in EU-Turkey relations and a search on both sides for new cooperation tools since the EUTRA was not a sufficient mechanism to handle mass population movements. Because the provision for the readmission of TCNs will be applicable as of 1 October 2017. The response to the Syrian mass migration first started with the EU–Turkey Joint Action Plan (JAP) in 2015, which focused on cooperation in accelerating

procedures for the readmission of irregular migrants who were not in need of international protection. Then, the EU–Turkey Statement (or EUTS)—an informal readmission tool—was signed on 18 March 2016 (European Council 2016).

The legal status was intensively discussed when the Council and Turkey agreed on the EUTS. However, the Court of Justice of the European Union by the Case T-192/16 (EDAL 2016) in 2017, as well as its decision regarding the appeal (CURIA 2018), showed that the EUTS is not seen as an international agreement under international law but non-binding soft law instruments. Also, at the national level, the EUTS was approached as a political statement, not an agreement, and thus was not submitted to the Turkish Parliament for approval as an international agreement; but a Directive on 5 April 2016 requesting the full support of all governmental bodies and local authorities to support the Presidency of Migration Management/ PMM (former Directorate/ DGMM) for implementation of the Statement under “Combating with Irregular Migration” heading (Presidency 2016).

As a crisis-driven readmission tool, the EUTS is directly connected to Syrians, and as a flexible form of readmission tool, it has different articles regarding the EU-Turkey relations from an external differentiated integration perspective. Regarding return and readmissions, Turkey agreed to accept all irregular migrants and asylum seekers whose applications were declared inadmissible, crossing from Turkey to the Greek islands on 20 March 2016 (Article 1) by the EUTS. The EUTS’s readmission-related commitments are also included in Arts 3 and 4 of the EUTRA. In this regard, the EUTS stepped within the terrain of the EU’s readmission competence, and the authorities were determined as the Council and the EP (Article 218 TFEU/ The Treaty of Lisbon, 2007).

The EUTS also created a mechanism for the return of Syrians via the ‘one-to-one’ formula. Accordingly, for every Syrian returned to Turkey from the Greek islands, another Syrian would be resettled in the EU (Article 2). Since the EUTS is not an international agreement but a bilateral statement, it needed a legal basis: the 2002 Readmission Protocol of Turkey and Greece (RPTG)⁷. The Protocol introduced the notion of a ‘safe third country’. Drawing on the Protocol, the EUTS paved the way for the immediate return of Syrian refugees arriving on the Greek islands because it defined Turkey as a ‘safe third country’⁸. However, Turkey’s “safe third country” position is criticised for several reasons: human rights violations that are reflected by the decisions of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), lack of legal protections, substandard conditions, political and social instability and international criticism regarding Turkey’s handling of asylum and migration, citing arbitrary detention, forced returns, and inadequate protection mechanisms (Ovacık et al. 2024). In particular, because its legal framework fails to provide adequate protection for non-Syrians, and the temporary protection regime for Syrians lacks the legal guarantees of the Geneva Convention (Yılmaz-Elmaz 2020).

The EUTS also mentions upgrading the customs union between Turkey and the EU and ‘re-energising the accession process’ for Turkey to obtain full membership. Incentives, such as capacity-building support and financial aid, were also included, with an additional €3 billion added to the amount agreed under the JAP. It has often been perceived as a blueprint for future cooperation models with other source and transit countries (Lehner 2019; Carrera et al. 2019; Gökalp-Aras 2019).

Although the Statement was mainly approached as an offer from the EU, both sides were willing to sign the EUTS. In particular, it suited Turkey’s changing strategy vis-à-vis migration and asylum-related issues after 2015 as Ankara’s demands—such as visa exemption, the customs union, and the accession process—were included. Naci Koru, who served as the Deputy Minister of Foreign Affairs (2012–2016) when the EUTS was being negotiated,

⁷ For the full text of the Protocol: <http://www.madde14.org/images/8/88/YunTurgerikabul.pdf>

⁸ The concept is based on the expresses the principle that refugees should seek asylum in the first safe country they are able to reach.

describes Turkey's negotiating proposal to the EU over the Statement as a 'game-changer' (Koru 2021a; GAR 2021):

We did not have to readmit Syrians, even if we had bilateral agreements. At this stage, the Statement was a game-changer. We offered to readmit Syrians and the other TCNs if they entered any of the five [nominated] Greek islands through Turkey. We knew that the EU would accept our offer right away. We thought those living in Turkey could continue living there after we readmitted them. However, if they had come from other countries—for example, Morocco—we agreed to return them to wherever they had come from (Koru 2021b).

In agreeing to readmit Syrians and other nationalities, Turkey's demands were visa exemption, financial support, revision of the customs union and a reset in EU–Turkey relations. According to the EUTRA, readmission for TCNs was suspended until 1 October 2017. Thus, the EUTS accelerated the readmission of TCNs, and on 4 April 2016, Turkey accepted the first readmitted group from Greece as a part of the EUTS (AIDA 2021). The RPTG was used as the legal basis for readmissions in implementing the EUTS until the EUTRA became applicable for TCNs in 2017. However, Turkey suspended the RPTG unilaterally on 6 June 2018 in response to a decision by a Greek court to release eight former Turkish soldiers who had fled the country a day after the 15 July 2016 coup attempt (TRT 2018).

In addition, after 1 October 2017, the EUTRA could not be used for TCNs, only for Turkish citizens, due to the administrative measures taken by Turkey based on delays regarding the visa exemption process. On 22 July 2019, the Turkish government publicly announced the suspension of the EUTRA in response to the EU sanctioning Turkey's gas drilling operations in Cypriot waters. However, Prime Minister Cavusoglu stated that 'this was not only due to the EU's recent sanctions. The decision was also taken because the EU still had not introduced the agreed-on visa-free regime for Turkish citizens (Euractiv 2019). He added that "the readmission agreement and visa-free deal [must] be put into effect simultaneously" (Daily Sabah 2019). In parallel, the EU's official websites indicated that the EUTS was still operating (European Commission 2020b; EASO 2020).

In 2016, Turkey began to hint that it might open its borders if the EU failed to meet its demands. This 'coercive migration diplomacy' remained strictly rhetorical until 28 February 2020, when Turkish authorities opened the border and allowed thousands of migrants and asylum seekers to walk into Greece. This came in response to attacks against the Turkish military in Idlib, Syria, threatening to send waves of new Syrian migrants into Turkey (Reuters 2020). Significantly, neither the EU nor Turkey repudiated the EUTS as this new crisis unfolded. While the EU offered financial support to both Greece and Turkey, Ankara's actions came in for strong criticism. However, on 9 March 2020, Turkish President Erdoğan, EU Council President Michel and EU Commission President von der Leyen reaffirmed that the EUTS remained valid and that the remaining outstanding provisions would be completed (Milliyet 2020).

Throughout March 2020, immigrants and refugees from various countries, including Syria, continued to gather at land and sea border areas on the Turkish side, including Edirne, Çanakkale, and İzmir. They were confronted with severe humanitarian tragedies and human rights violations in attempting to cross into Europe. By 28 March, Turkish state actors had begun to round up most of these migrants and distribute them to satellite cities inside Turkey. When the crisis ended on 27 March, the EU Commission Spokesman Peter Stano stated, "Negotiations and evaluations regarding the EU–Turkey Statement [would] continue" (Anadolu Agency 2020). Against this backdrop, the new EU Pact (2020) explicitly mentions Turkey as the reference case and foregrounds the importance of the EUTS as a model.

5. Turkey's Approach Towards Readmissions and Returns

The findings of the first fieldwork conducted in 2010–2013 (İzmir, Edirne and Ankara) confirm Turkey's conditionality, reservations and critical approach to the EUTS. The results reflect the significant problems regarding EUTRAs and the Turkey case. The respondents repeatedly mentioned the risks that Turkey might become a migration “buffer zone” or “dumping ground” for the EU.

Respondents assessed Turkey's request for visa liberation as a fair demand that had successfully elevated the EUTRA as a negotiation leverage point. Also, the majority of respondents emphasised burden-sharing problems with both the EU and Greece, challenges in implementing RAs and Turkey's lack of capacity to expel migrants:

If Turkey signs this Agreement [EUTRA], we must accept those who have been apprehended in Greece. They will insist that all those illegal migrants come from Turkey. Every migrant will be given a simple line to repeat over and over: 'I came from Turkey'. After taking these migrations back from Greece, how is Turkey supposed to return them to their origin countries without readmission agreements with those countries? This [return] is too costly for Turkey to implement (Interview with a local journalist, 2012, Edirne).

The following quote details Turkey's complex implementation of the RPTG and, more importantly, the further implementation of the EUTS.

I do not think that Turkey will sign the Agreement [EUTRA]. Even if it is signed, it will be impossible to implement. We already have a protocol with Greece, but it has not been appropriately implemented. For example, if there are 100,000 units [migrants], we only accept 3,000 units, and only if there is sufficient evidence that they came from Turkey. The readmission agreement is a part of the bargaining process, and I do not think it can go beyond this (interview with a high-level public officer, 2013, Ankara).

The respondents who had a role in implementation provided a more precise picture of existing practices and problems and the possible future of the RPTG and the EUTRA. Most law enforcement officers emphasised the problems Turkey faced after readmission, particularly the economic burden of sending them to their country of origin and the lack of readmission agreements with those countries. A high-level Ministry of Foreign Affairs bureaucrat stated that “Turkey does not apply this Protocol [the RPTG] and will continue not to. Turkey will likely sign the readmission agreement with the EU, but it does not mean we will implement it” (interview with a high-level MFA officer, 2013, Ankara). Indeed, a few months after these interviews, the EUTRA was signed and then ratified, but as mentioned, Turkey has not implemented the provisions relating to third-country nationals despite these entering into force in October 2017 (European Commission 2020c).

The second fieldwork revealed continuity in Turkey's conditional approach and implementation challenges. The crisis-driven EUTS emerged as a more flexible, tailor-made deal compared to the standard EURAs, addressing the immediate demands of both sides. The respondents highlighted Turkey's conditionality and the potential implementation problems regarding the Agreement. Following the 2015 crisis, both sides could reach a consensus for the EUTS, a crisis-driven, more flexible and tailor-made deal responding to both sides' demands.

An NGO representative, who has been highly active in the field and provided regular support during the implementation of the EUTS, summarised the EUTS, its underlying rationale, and the implementation process from the perspective of both their organisation and their viewpoint.

In 2015-16, following Merkel's announcement, the influx wasn't only for Syrians. While 6,000 Iranians used to come annually, in 2016-17, these numbers reached 60,000. Therefore, the EU and Turkey wanted to convey the message: "If you try to go to Europe through irregular means, we will send you back. But if you stay in Turkey and apply, we will take you". This was accepted for a while. However, from the second half of 2018, it stopped functioning due to the length of these waiting periods, the inefficacy of the one-for-one formula, and the unequal distribution of this responsibility among EU member states (interview with the representative of an NGO, 2018, Ankara).

The fieldwork showed that the readmission and return, specifically the EUTS and its implementation, became highly politicised and centralised. During the second fieldwork, Turkey was still under a state of emergency following the attempted coup d'état on 15 July 2016, and the field of migration and asylum had already been intensively centralised and securitised. The respondents stated the impact of the domestic policy through the coup attempt on 15 July 2016 in Turkey and the Fethullah Gülen Terrorist Organisation (FETO) operations,

From our side [Turkey], there are no pushbacks, but Greece does. In particular, after the terrorist incidents [FETO], it needs to be reported if a bird flies over the sea. If someone crosses the border from the sea and does not stop, everybody [the coast guards] will face a severe problem (interview with the representative of an IGO, 2018, İzmir).

During the second fieldwork, the non-state meso level actors were excluded from the implementation of the EUTS due to the increased securitisation. Turkey's increasing concerns regarding securitisation and the visible domestic and foreign policy nexus regarding return policy appear to be significant observations in the field. Including the return and readmissions, the entire process has been centrally conducted as a closed box without proper oversight or monitoring.

The February-March 2020 events (known as Pazarkule) at the Turkey-Greece border meant the 'de facto' end of the EUTS, and the readmissions were stopped. Turkish Foreign Ministry Spokesperson stated that due to the COVID-19 outbreak worldwide and to protect public health, the EU temporarily suspended the important element of the EUTS resettlement program. For the same reason, Turkey also temporarily stopped the readmission process for refugees and reported this to the Greek authorities. The last readmission was completed in March 2020 with 23 readmissions (UNHCR 2020), confirmed by NGOs, IGOs and the EU representatives as part of the second tranche of fieldwork.

Data gathered during fieldwork's first and second parts reflect important continuities in Turkey's demands, particularly regarding the visa exemption. However, the impact of Syrian mass migration was most apparent in the second tranche of fieldwork. A critical theme that appears in particular for the second fieldwork is that the EUTS and EUTRA became parts of high politics, and securitisation increased due to domestic policy changes. Turkey has been emphasising its expectations from the EUTS, such as renewal of and also to continue operating while considering the other dimensions, such as accession perspective, updating the Customs Union, visa liberalisation, development of migration cooperation, cooperation in the fight against terrorism, high-level dialogue and operation of established institutional mechanisms (Kaymakçı 2022). Regarding the future of the EUTS, the permanent representative of Turkey to the EU, Faruk Kaymakçı, stated that a review is needed to reflect Turkey's emerging requirements and revise the financial component. He added that financial aid should be re-calculated according to current data—today, 4.7 million Syrian and non-Syrian migrants live in Turkey—and that the new agreement should be expanded to include other nationalities (ibid.). However, the future of the EUTS remains an essential and highly discussed question. Since March 2016, 2,139 returns have been completed under its terms (PMM 2021), and during the third fieldwork, the renewal of the EUTS is still expected, while the number of border crossings has started to increase again.

6. Current Situation, Practices, and Future Projections

As of the date this paper was written, the EUTS has completed its eighth year. Although Turkey suspended the implementation of the returns component in March 2020 and stopped readmissions of TCNs from Greece, the EUTS's effects and the expectations regarding its renewal remain prominent in both the political agenda and academic studies. Despite the suspension of the return component in March 2020 by Turkey, the EU kept its two promises regarding financial support (through the Facility of Refugees in Turkey/ FRIT as 6 billion) and the 1:1 resettlement scheme (to resettle a Syrian from Turkey to the EU for every Syrian being returned to Turkey from Greek islands), and still implementing. As of 4 July 2024, 67.441 Syrians have been resettled under the 1:1 resettlement scheme since 2016, while representing still a small proportion of the total number of Syrians is 3.1 million (PMM 2024).

As of 2017, the EU stopped reporting, especially for the EUTS, but the 7th evaluation report of the EC regarding the FRIT provides updates. Accordingly, the "One-for-One" resettlement scheme under the Statement continued, resettling 37,397 Syrian refugees from Turkey to the EU between April 2016 and February 2023. Since 2016, 2,140 migrants have been returned from the Greek islands to Turkey. However, Turkish authorities have maintained their March 2020 suspension of return operations, and no returns have occurred since then despite repeated requests from Greek authorities and the EC (European Commission 2023b, 3-4).

The EC's report (ibid.) emphasises the significant efforts of Turkey to host and address the needs of more than four million refugees and mentions that "The Statement continued to deliver results in 2022". The report also highlights the increasing number of irregular arrivals and their importance and reminds us of Turkey's suspension of returns from Greek islands.

However, from both sides, publicly available data is limited. We do not know how many returned persons could apply or have been rejected for international protection in Turkey, what are the selection criteria for the 1:1 settlement scheme, whether the EUTRA could be implemented for the Turkish nationals or the TCNs, details about the EUTRA's and the EUTS's suspension remain unclear, including the provisions of the Implementing Protocol between Turkey and Bulgaria (Ovacik et al. 2024).

There is no progress regarding visa liberalisation, full membership, the Customs Union or the Voluntary Humanitarian Admission Scheme (Ibid.). The 7th EC Report mentioned the precondition for the Scheme, which "sustainably reduced irregular crossings between Turkey and the EU" (European Commission 2023, 4). It seems the renewed priorities must be rediscussed as incentives for those who have lost their credibility and to strengthen relations and cooperation.

Despite these unclear dimensions, the third fieldwork provided important preliminary findings for the EUTRA and the EUTS. The number of interviews conducted with state actors is still limited. However, from the selected cities and the related meso level actors, there are significant findings for the practices during implementing the return component until March 2020 and future protections.

During the third and the most recent fieldwork (January-July 2024), the main focus of the meso level and mainly non-state or IGO respondents was on the EUTS, with its potential renewal, foresight regarding new conditions for its renewal and its implications in Turkey. The most important finding regarding the consequences of suspension is the increased pushbacks and informal returns. One of the most significant impacts of the EUTS's suspension has been increased informal returns, commonly called pushbacks. Greece, facing a substantial accumulation of migrants at its borders, has resorted to unofficial pushback practices. These actions, while not legally sanctioned, reflect the practical challenges and political tensions

surrounding the management of migration flows. While Greece's actions can be categorised as pushbacks, the term might not fully capture the nature of Turkey's response. Pushbacks typically imply the immediate expulsion of individuals attempting to cross the border. The respondents, mainly the NGO representatives and locals at the border cities, villages and critical border-crossing points, generally claimed that despite suspending the return component, Greece continued its action with pushback.

In contrast, the field study suggests that Turkey's actions involve not only expelling individuals but also facilitating their passage back towards Greece, a practice that might be more accurately described as "push-through"⁹, which became publicly visible in 2020 (known as Pazarkule events) at the Turkey-Greece borders. However, according to the high number of respondents, including from the border villages, this action was started before Pazarkule and intensively continues after and now as being shifted from the Turkey-Greece border to the Turkey-Bulgaria border continues. It is also stated that Greece significantly stopped pushbacks to Turkey but now to Bulgaria, which also explains the changing location for Turkey's claimed "push-through" actions. In the context of Turkey's response to these pushbacks, "push-through" seems to be a more fitting term as capturing the idea that Turkey is not just returning individuals to their point of entry but is actively facilitating their movement back across the border into Greece. This proactive engagement goes beyond preventing entry and involves a deliberate effort to send individuals back through the border, reflecting a coordinated and systematic approach. Using "push-through" can help to differentiate between the more passive act of pushback and the active role that Turkey appears to be taking in ensuring these individuals are returned to Greece. This term emphasises the ongoing cycle of returns and highlights the dynamic and reciprocal nature of the migration management practices between the two countries. The following quotes from the NGO representatives' interviews highlight pushbacks, non-refoulement violations, and critiques for the EU and MSs.

Actually, Greece discovered that unofficially conducting pushbacks was a practical and economical approach after the EUTS. They also realised that the enforcement power of the EU, EU criteria, principles, UN resolutions, and the European Convention on Human Rights was ineffective. Turkey can respond to the questions and criticisms with, "Well, we learned this from Greece,". It would be understandable. (interview with the representative of an NGO, 2024, Ankara).

Another NGO representative highlighted the reasons why the EUTS could not be implemented and how hypocrisy can arise when EU interests are at stake, particularly regarding human rights violations.

The EUTS was not implemented and remained with only around 30,000 admissions. One of the reasons for this lack of implementation is the Greek authorities' limited capacity, but pushbacks reduced their migrant stock to Turkey. This situation is convenient for Greece and aligns with the broader EU perspective, which often prioritises EU interests before discussing human rights. For instance, when Süleyman Soylu said, "Since 2019, we have stopped 2,560,000 people at the border," it essentially means that we have violated non-refoulement. Of course, this is also understood by the EU and human rights defenders within the EU. But it means the EU borders are protected (interview with the representative of an NGO, 2024, Ankara).

⁹ The author believes that, in the context of Turkey's response to these pushbacks, "push-through" seems to be a more fitting term as capturing the idea that Turkey is not just returning individuals to their point of entry but is actively facilitating their movement back across the border into Greece. This proactive engagement goes beyond the mere act of preventing entry and involves a deliberate effort to send individuals back through the border, reflecting a coordinated and systematic approach. Using "push-through" can help to differentiate between the more passive act of pushbacks and the active role that Turkey appears to be taking in ensuring these individuals are returned to Greece. This term emphasizes the ongoing cycle of returns and highlights the dynamic and reciprocal nature of the migration management practices between the two countries.

Regarding the pushback and push-through by Greece and Turkey, the following quote from a border village in Edirne shows the situation after Pazarkule and in recent days.

Greece has been pushing them to our side for a long time. They come in all conditions, injured, beaten. Sometimes, we find bodies, too, as fish have eaten their legs or they have decayed. There were many in 2020 at Pazarkule. It continued for 6-7 months after the pandemic arrived badly. The governor's office provided clothes, thermal blankets, and food supplies. The smugglers are well-known here; as Greece pushes and deports them, we send [sallyoruz¹⁰] them off from here. I'm a boatman, and there were weeks when I sent off 4-5 busloads. The military was already there, infantry soldiers. Before and after Pazarkule, even commandos and special forces came too; sometimes, they gathered here (village) in large numbers. In the village square, for example, I say 400, and you say 500 people. It has decreased a bit lately, but the village square was full just last week. Greece pushes them from there, and we send [sallyoruz] them off from here (interview with a local and human smuggler, 2024, Edirne).

During the fieldwork, another significant finding was the foresight and perceptions about the renewal of the EUTS. While the state actors highlighted Turkey's expectation for the EU to support its cross-border development activities and expand the safe zone in the Northwest of Syria for returns in parallel to the second fieldwork's findings. It was stated that non-state actors believe the 1:1 formula could be applied more effectively this time with Greece and that the EU and Turkey are in new and significant cooperation regarding returns. There is an expectation that the EU's financial and capacity support for Turkey's evolving and increasingly visible national return mechanism will be included in the renewed EUTS.

Under the framework of the EU-Turkey Statement, the new agreement will likely establish a special positioning between Greece and Turkey regarding the Readmission Agreement and the new Statement. This policy will likely develop primarily through the one-for-one formula directly between Greece and Turkey (interview with the representative of an NGO, 2024, Ankara).

The following two quotes provide an understanding of Turkey's expectations for the EU in general regarding the return policy and, in particular, for the new conditions of the renewal of the EUTS.

After our military operations, we approached those regions entirely from a humanitarian perspective and made many investments. Gaziantep University has a School of Health Sciences in the area. We established an industrial zone in Çobanbey, and even last week, an international fair was held with the participation of businesspeople from various Arab countries. We have hospitals and health services in the region. We are creating educational and job opportunities. However, the region needs more investment. The EU and other Western countries need to support these safe zones. In Gaziantep alone, the number of people I am concerned with is greater than the number of refugees in Europe (interview with the state official, 2024, Gaziantep).¹¹

We [Turkey] requested that the ESSN (Emergency Social Safety Net)¹² support from the EU not be cut off when people return to Syria, and the EU did not accept our offer. These safe areas need to receive more investment, and development in the region needs to be encouraged (interview with the state official, 2024, Gaziantep).¹³

¹⁰ The term "sallyoruz" [in Turkish language] actually means facilitating illegal border crossings. This is how it is expressed locally. For Greece, the term "deportation" is predominantly used.

¹¹ This interview was conducted by Umutcan Yüksel, a researcher from the SRII team and his consent for using this quotation was obtained.

¹² The ESSN is the largest humanitarian cash programme that assisting over 1.5 million refugees, primarily individuals living under temporary and international protection in Turkey.

¹³ See #8.

Regarding the financial dimension of the JAP and the EUTS, the following quote highlights the unfair share of responsibilities and miscalculations and assumptions of Turkey.

In the Netherlands, the cost of one person to the state is 65 Euros per day. The annual cost for this person is approximately 23,650 Euros. For 1 million people per year, this amounts to 23 billion Euros. When we talk about a population of 4 million in Turkey at that time, this is roughly 100 billion Euros for one year. However, the amount offered to Turkey by the EU was 3+3 billion Euros. Turkey's biggest mistake is not doing these kinds of analyses and not sitting at the negotiation table. They act as if Turkey is obliged to host these people anyway (interview with the representative of an NGO, 2024, Ankara).

Regarding the practices during the initial implementation of the return component of the EUTS, the interviewed limited legal practitioners who had cases of the returnees as a part of the EUTS stated that although the readmissions were operated only at a town called Dikili (close to İzmir, Turkey), later, there were two main removal centres (RCs) were used. It is noted that as of 1 April 2016, initially, individuals were transferred from Greece's Lesbos Island to Dikili and were placed in Edirne and Kırklareli, which are two Turkish provinces. Pehlivan köy Removal Centre was specifically opened following the EUTS. There were logistical and procedural issues in implementing the EUTS, including the dual issuance of deportation orders by different administrative bodies, which led to legal challenges. For example, initial deportation orders by the İzmir Provincial Directorate of Migration Management were followed by additional orders by the Kırklareli Governorship, leading to court cases and subsequent annulments due to procedural violations. The process saw a significant involvement of administrative and judicial bodies, and despite initial procedural setbacks, the practice continued with the transfer of individuals to return centres in a remote province such as Kayseri by mid-2017.

The respondents highlighted multiple instances of human rights violations, which were reported by them during the process, including forced deportations and inadequate consideration of asylum claims. Many individuals, particularly non-Syrians like Bangladeshis, Myanmarese, and Pakistanis, were subject to rapid deportations without adequate legal recourse. Specific cases highlight the lack of effective legal oversight and the potential for abuse, such as forcing individuals to sign voluntary return forms under duress and inadequate protection for those at risk of persecution.

The findings for this initial period showed that the EUTS had faced numerous operational challenges, including the capacity limitations of Greek authorities to process returns, the bureaucratic complexity of the system, and the mixed effectiveness of implementation across different regions. The practices under the EUTS often involved significant variations in the treatment and processing of migrants depending on their nationality and specific circumstances.

Those legal practitioners and lawyers have also emphasised the pushback practices as a significant issue, which often involve the use of force and intimidation, and there are documented cases of severe mistreatment of migrants at the borders. It is stated that there have been systemic pushbacks from both Bulgaria and Greece, with different practices observed, such as the involvement of third-party nationals in executing pushbacks in Greece and direct military involvement in Bulgaria.

For the prospects regarding the EUTRA and EUTS, the third part of the research showed that Turkey has been developing its border management and taking the necessary measures to prevent the opening of any new sea or land routes for irregular migration from Turkey to the EU, such as re-introduction of visa requirements for those Syrians travelling to Turkey by air and sea from a third country in 2016 (Ovacik et al. 2024). However, despite the increased measures at the borders, there has been a steady decrease in irregular border crossings because

of domestic and foreign policy developments, such as the Taliban's takeover in 2021 and the completed border walls at the Syrian and Iran borders as of September 2023.

In addition, Turkey's national return mechanisms have advanced significantly, incorporating sophisticated technologies and coordinated efforts to manage migration. Such as the introduction of new migration control tools, the Mobile Migration Points (MMPs) equipped with advanced fingerprinting technologies for identification and Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Centres that work 24/7, accelerated deportations, and cause invisibility. Most importantly, parallel to the new generation of readmission tools, they create "informality" along with the increased pushbacks. In addition, along with the voluntary return and reintegration programme (AVRR) with the IOM, which started in 2009, with the collaboration of the ICMPD, the national AVRR (N-AVRR) mechanism was established in 2022 (Mencütek Şahin 2023). However, the multi-sited fieldwork displayed severe legal and implementation problems regarding detention and deportation practices. Ovacık et al. (2024, 169) argue that concerning those practices in Turkey, including many cases, ECtHR ruled on the case Akkad v. Turkey (BVMN 2022) as that also fits the typical profile of the EUTS, Turkey should not be considered a safe third country for returns from EU Member States. However, rather than changing Turkey's "safe third country" status, the main expectation appears to be capacity building and financial support from the renewed EUTS.

7. Conclusion

This article has analysed the EU's return and external policy instruments using Turkey as a case study and focusing on two critical readmission instruments—the EUTRA of 2013 and the EUTS from 2016. The longitudinal research displayed the complexity of readmissions to the fore showcased, how readmission tools are interpreted and instrumentalised by the EU and Turkey, and how differentiated integration has become the norm of the EU return policy. It has shed much-needed light on TCS' strategies to resist EU externalisation efforts, particularly their cost-benefit calculations in engagement with the EU on returns and readmissions.

The article displays that Turkey has leveraged conditionality in its favour rather than being a passive policy receiver. Since the Syrian mass migration, it has deployed migration as a foreign policy tool to accomplish various objectives. This was apparent in negotiations over the EUTRA in 2013, but Turkey had expanded its demands by the EUTS in 2016. The EUTS presented that this temporary and extraordinary measure or purportedly 'exceptional' readmission strategy has become the new norm, particularly after the EU Pact. Despite its failures, the EUTS has served as a blueprint for other countries, and the EU Pact confirms expectations regarding similar bilateral cooperation with non-European countries going forward.

The EUTRA and the subsequent EUTS represent pivotal moments in the externalisation of EU migration policy. Despite their significant aims, the practical outcomes and operational challenges highlight the complexities and limitations inherent in these agreements. The suspension of the readmission components of these agreements by Turkey since 2020 has led to a critical shift in migration dynamics in the region. Greece, facing substantial migrant accumulation at its borders, has resorted to informal pushback practices, which, although not legally sanctioned, illustrate the tensions and practical difficulties in managing migration flows. Turkey's response to these pushbacks has been characterised by actions that could be termed "push-through," where individuals are expelled and facilitated back towards Greece. This term captures the reciprocal and escalatory nature of border enforcement tactics between these two nations.

Moreover, the fieldwork conducted in Edirne and İzmir underscores the dual nature of Turkey's national return mechanisms. On the one hand, significant efforts are being made to facilitate voluntary returns to safe zones in Northern Syria, reflecting Turkey's strategic

interest in stabilising these regions and reducing its domestic burden. In this context, during the renewal process of the EUTS, there have been notable expectations for the support of Turkey's national return mechanism, particularly for capacity building and the strengthening and further expansion of the safe zone established by Turkey in Northern Syria were highlighted by the meso-level respondents.

The findings underscore the complexities and political sensitivities surrounding the EUTS and EUTRA. The evolving nature of EU-Turkey migration cooperation highlights the need for more balanced and comprehensive approaches that address immediate migration management needs and the underlying causes of displacement. Future agreements must reconcile the practicalities of border control with the imperatives of human rights and sustainable development, ensuring that policies are effective, ethical, and just. The EU's shift towards informalisation and differentiated externalisation must be carefully managed to avoid undermining the broader goals of stability, security, and respect for international law.

This case study enhances our understanding of readmission arrangements and externalisation policies by showcasing Turkey's strategic use of conditionality and leveraging its geopolitical position in EU negotiations. Future research should examine the evolving EU-Turkey migration dynamics, the long-term effects of informal readmission agreements, and the roles of other non-EU countries in similar externalisation agreements to gain broader insights into global migration governance.

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